

ELIXIR Community Review - Process & Outcomes Form

Name of the ELIXIR Community	Reviewers:
Date	Presenters:

For information:

Review purpose

The purpose of the review is to capture and assess progress of an ELIXIR Community, based on developments and success since the Community establishment. It also represents an opportunity for Communities to showcase their success, and express their needs for specific support from ELIXIR. Furthermore, it should cover and be used to reflect upon established Community aims, based on the existing white paper/roadmap and elucidate foreseen directions to be taken and technical developments as well as scientific areas to be covered in the upcoming 5-10 years. ELIXIR will also aim to use the gathered information to determine best practices to be fed back to the Communities.

This review is part of the ELIXIR Community evolution. The Community review is fully internal to ELIXIR. The review Committee will report feedback to the ELIXIR Heads of Nodes. In specific cases, the internal review can be replaced e.g. through a review conducted by the ELIXIR Scientific Advisory Board.

Review format & preparation

The review meeting will be scheduled for one hour, starting with a 15 min presentation by the Community, 20-30 min for questions/comments and followed by a 15-25 min closed session where the Review Committee can discuss first-hand feedback. The schedule will be strictly monitored to ensure an efficient meeting, thus, the presentation by the Community can not exceed 15 minutes.

The review criteria as outlined below is shared with the Community co-leads and the Review Committee prior to the review, allowing the Community co-leads to prepare a 15 min review presentation, addressing the main review criteria (see below). A standard [ELIXIR slide template](#) can be used, without a specific structure to follow. The co-leads are not expected to prepare other material than the slides prior to the review meeting. The Review Committee will be pointed to the Community webpages for context prior to the review.

The review date will be announced to the Community co-leads and the Review Committee one month prior to the review date, together with the review details. The review outcome is a maximum of three page report that will be presented to the Heads of Nodes for information at the next available meeting.

Review Committee

The Review Committee is invited by the ELIXIR Director and made up of a combination of Heads of Nodes and other Node officials, such as Technical and Training Coordinators, co-leads of other ELIXIR Communities and Platform ExCos.

The Review Committee will typically consist of four reviewers, and is chaired by a senior Committee member. One to two ELIXIR Hub representatives will join the review.

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Acknowledgements: Susanna Repo (ELIXIR Finland)

The Review Committee's responsibility is to conduct the review and share comments based on the presented criteria. Hub representatives will support the report finalisation. Once finalised a Review Committee member will give a short update at the next HoNs meeting.

Review Outcome

The Review Committee will produce a written review, based on the review criteria below. The report is shared with the Heads of Nodes prior to their consecutive meeting. Once shared with the HoN the review report will also be shared with the Community co-leads/Community review presenters from the respective Community.

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ELIXIR Community Review Assessment Criteria

For completion by the Review Committee (total maximum of three pages; italic section descriptions can be deleted)

1) Community Organisation and Scope

Community leadership, membership, structure and engagement with ELIXIR Platforms, other ELIXIR Communities and Focus Groups

Comment on the broadness of ELIXIR representation within the Community; are Nodes well represented; diversity inclusion and equity aspects; links and interactions within ELIXIR (level of “connectedness”); how are ideas and outputs shared within the Community and across ELIXIR?

Scientific focus, scope, need and future needs, link to the wider (non-ELIXIR) community

Highlight the ELIXIR Community’s contributions to the scientific field, illustrate the importance of the ELIXIR Community focus, and its fit into the life sciences (linking to the bigger picture). Consider the counter-factual aspects, if the Community didn’t exist, what would be missing? Explain the relevance of the Community’s work to the needs of the wider (non-ELIXIR) community and users; are the ELIXIR Community and wider community goals aligned; is there scope for the Community to grow.

2) Community Success

Is the Community on the path to accomplish the goals defined in the white paper/roadmap?

Highlight progress towards the Community white paper/roadmap goals (is progress as foreseen, faster or slower). This can also be linked to Implementation Study progress/outcomes. What content has created value for Community members?

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Community activities in support of the [current ELIXIR Scientific Programme](#)

Comment on the alignment of the Community activities with the [five strategic objectives](#) of the 2019-2023 Programme.

3) Community Impact (in the context of ELIXIR and beyond)

ELIXIR's [impact areas](#) can be used as a reference.

Technical Contribution

Is the technical contribution of the Community of high quality and current? Comment on e.g. developed services, quality of science (conference presentations, publications, funding awards, ...). Are there any aspects to highlight? Are there examples of the Community collaborating with ELIXIR Platforms and other Communities to demonstrate impact?

Additional Community Impact

What Impact did the Community make, did the Community share concrete success stories to showcase impact? What is the current Community legacy and who is it useful and valuable to the desired audience?

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4) Final summary and recommendations

Provide a final summary of the ELIXIR Community as a whole. If necessary, please provide any suggestions for improvement or modification, including recommendations regarding significant gaps and opportunities, which could be explored. Feel free to add any other comments to be considered.